

Effect of nickel doping on the structural and optical characteristics of magnesium ferrite.

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Abstract

This research work investigates the impact of nickel (Ni) doping on the structural and optical properties of magnesium ferrite (MgFe_2O_4). Magnesium ferrite is a promising material with numerous applications in the fields of electronics, catalysis, and magnetic devices due to its unique magnetic and optical properties. In this paper, the MgFe_2O_4 is synthesised by solid state reaction method and nickel doped magnesium ferrite is synthesised by sol-gel auto combustion method and both are annealed at 500°C . The structural and optical characteristics of these nanoparticles were systematically analysed. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis revealed that the crystal structure of magnesium ferrite remained unchanged upon nickel doping, indicating successful substitution of magnesium and iron ions with nickel ions. Spinel ferrite is identified as the material by FTIR and Raman investigation. UV-Visible spectroscopy was employed to investigate the optical properties. It was observed that nickel doping significantly influenced the optical absorption and bandgap of magnesium ferrite, leading to alterations in the absorption edge and energy levels of the material. These changes in the optical characteristics have important implications for the potential applications of nickel-doped magnesium ferrite in optoelectronic devices and photocatalysis. The results of this study provide valuable insights into the tunability of magnesium ferrite's optical properties through nickel doping, expanding the understanding of this material's potential for a wide range of technological applications.

Keywords: Magnesium ferrite, Ni-doped magnesium ferrite, XRD, FTIR, Raman spectroscopy.

Introduction

Spinel ferrites refer to a class of materials that possess a unique crystal structure known as the spinel structure. The spinel structure consists of oxygen ions forming a close-packed cubic lattice, with metal cations occupying both tetrahedral and octahedral sites within the lattice. The general chemical formula for spinel ferrites is AB_2O_4 , where A and B represent different metal cations. Spinel ferrites have attracted significant research interest due to their diverse properties and potential applications in various fields. They exhibit a range of magnetic, electrical and dielectric, catalytic, and optical properties, applicable to energy storage and conversion, sensing applications. The properties can be tailored by adjusting the composition and doping of the A and B metal cations as per requirement. Among various metal ferrites, magnesium ferrite ($MgFe_2O_4$) is a very common semiconducting material. High resistivity and permeability make it a widely accepted semiconductor material. Apart from that, magnesium ferrite possesses high ferromagnetic resistivity, Curie temperature. At the same time, it has low electrical loss [1-3]. In metal ferrites, the distribution of cations plays the steering role in controlling magnetic, electrical, and structural properties. Properties of the mother metal ferrite can be tailored by doping different metal ions within it. Researchers have doped several metal ions viz., Co^{+2} [1], Zn^{+2} [4], Ni^{+2} [5] etcetera into $MgFe_2O_4$ and studied the characteristics. Among these spinel ferrites, Ni-doped $MgFe_2O_4$ has attracted considerable attention due to its unique properties and potential applications in diverse fields, including electronics, catalysis, spintronic devices [6] and energy storage. Specifically, $NiFe_2O_4$ gaining much attention because of its superior properties [7]. Most interestingly, $NiFe_2O_4$ has inverse spinel structure leading to significant electronic conduction [8, 9]. Mg^{+2} and Ni^{+2} ions occupy the tetrahedral (A) sites, while Fe^{+3} ions occupy both the octahedral (B) and tetrahedral (A) sites. The change in bond length for tetrahedral and octahedral lattice sites often plays a main role in the varying doping of electrons [10, 11]. This arrangement results in a mixed valence state of Fe ions, which significantly influences the material's properties. The presence of both divalent and trivalent cations introduces charge imbalance and creates oxygen vacancies, leading to enhanced electrical conductivity and catalytic activity. It is noteworthy that, incorporation of ferromagnetic nickel into non-magnetic magnesium enhances its magnetic properties. Ni^{+2} ions possess a different electron configuration compared to Fe^{+3} ions, leading to changes in the magnetic coupling and spin interactions within the lattice. This modification can result in altered magnetic properties, such as enhanced magnetization, modified magnetic anisotropy, and improved magnetostrictive behavior, making Ni-doped

MgFe₂O₄ suitable for applications in magnetic devices and sensors. Generally, nickel-based ferrites are used as a soft magnets and low loss material at high frequencies. [12]. Ni-doped MgFe₂O₄ exhibits unique properties resulting from the incorporation of Ni ions into the spinel ferrite lattice. Doping can also influence the optical properties of MgFe₂O₄. By introducing nickel, the absorption and emission properties of the material can be modified, allowing for tailored optical characteristics [13-15].

This work aims to contribute the understanding and comparative study of the structural and optical properties of MgFe₂O₄ and Mg_{0.5}Ni_{0.5}Fe₂O₄ which highlight the key differences and similarities between these materials. Through a comprehensive analysis, we will scabble into their crystal structures, band gaps, absorption spectra, and other optical properties. Understanding these characteristics will provide valuable information for designing and developing novel materials with enhanced optical and magnetic functionalities.

Materials and methods

Synthesis of compounds

The compound magnesium ferrite (MgFe₂O₄) was synthesized by solid state reaction method. The other one i.e., nickel-doped magnesium ferrite (Mg_{0.5}Ni_{0.5}Fe₂O₄) was synthesized by sol-gel auto-combustion process. Both the compounds were annealed at 500°C separately. The precursor for magnesium ferrite was prepared using nitrates of Mg²⁺ and Fe³⁺ ions. More specifically, Mg(NO₃)₂.6H₂O, Fe(NO₃)₃.9H₂O, NaOH, and NaCl were mixed in a molar ratio (1:2:8:2) and ground together in an agate mortar for about 30min. As the reaction proceeded, the mixture became mushy and underwent gradual changes in colour from blue (3min) to finally brown (10min). This mixture was washed with deionized water several times. After the removal of sodium chloride by washing, the powders were dried at 80°C for 2h. The powders were then calcined at 500°C for 5 hours.

For the synthesis of nickel-doped magnesium ferrite (Mg_{0.5}Ni_{0.5}Fe₂O₄), Mg(NO₃)₂.6H₂O, Ni(NO₃)₂.6H₂O, Fe(NO₃)₃.9H₂O were used as precursors. Each compound was poured in separate beakers in stoichiometric ratios containing specified volume of distilled water and stirred for 40 mins. Distilled water is added to a separate beaker containing appropriate amount of acetic acid (C₆H₈O₇·H₂O). To ensure proper dissolution, all beakers are placed on separate stirrers and stirred simultaneously for 40 minutes. The solution from the precursor's beakers is then transferred while continuously stirring. Gradual addition of ammonia maintains the pH at 7.0. The mixture is consistently stirred at approximately 90 °C for 6 hours

until a yellow gel forms. This gel is collected and dried in a hot air oven at 100 °C for 24 hours. The product was then annealed within a furnace at 500°C for 5 hours. After cooled down, the product was taken out of the furnace and meshed into fine powders for further characterization.

Characterization

X-ray diffractogram using “X’ Pert PRO PANalytical” (Cu-K α , = 0.15418 nm, 40 kV) was captured to identify and measure crystal size and structure. The crystal size was determined using the “Scherrer formula” derived from the XRD peak. The samples were examined using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (NICOLET 6700, USA) in order to analyze compositional features. Field emission SEM (ZEISS EVO 60) was used for capturing the micrographs of ferrites. The structural characteristics of these ferrites were examined using Raman spectroscopy (Spectra Physics, USA). Absorbance was measured by ultraviolet visible (UV) spectroscopy.

Results and discussions

Crystal structural analysis

The X-ray diffractograms of the un-doped and Ni-doped MgFe₂O₄ is shown in Fig. 1. In the diffractograms no extra peaks other than cubic spinel structure have been observed. It confirms about the purity of the prepared samples. For pure MgFe₂O₄ the diffraction peaks corresponding to (220), (311), (222), (400), (511) and (440) confirms the FCC spinel structure within 25° to 70° diffraction angle (JCPDS, Card No.10- 325). In case of nickel-doped magnesium ferrite one additional peak corresponding to (422) appeared. Being the highest peak among all, the crystalline parameters corresponding to (311) for both pure and doped MgFe₂O₄ is shown in Table 1. Significant variation in crystal parameters can be observed due to doping of nickel into magnesium ferrite spinel. Nelson Relay’s function (Eq. 1) was used to find lattice constant [16].

$$a = d_{hkl}(h^2 + k^2 + l^2)^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

Where “*hkl*” are Miller indices corresponding to a crystalline plane, ‘*d_{hkl}*’ is the corresponding interplanar spacing between the crystalline lattice plane, and ‘*a*’ is the lattice constant. Average crystallite size was calculated using Scherrer’s formula (*D_S*) (Eq. 2) [17], Williams-Hall equation (*D_{W-H}*) (Eq. 3) [18], and size-strain plot (*D_{SSP}*) (Eq. 4) [19].

$$D_s = \frac{4\lambda}{\beta \cos\theta} \quad (2)$$

$$\beta \cos\theta = \frac{0.9\lambda}{D_{W-H}} + 4\varepsilon \sin\theta \quad (3)$$

$$\left(\frac{d_{hkl} \beta \cos\theta}{\lambda}\right)^2 = \frac{0.75}{D_{SSP}} \left(\frac{d_{hkl}^2 \beta \cos\theta}{\lambda}\right) + (2\varepsilon)^2 \quad (4)$$

Where, ' β ' is the FWHM of the (311) peak, ' θ ' is the Bragg's diffraction angle of (311) peaks, and ' λ ' is the wavelength of X-ray beam (1.54 Å).the value of micro-strain (ε) was calculated using Eq.5.

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\beta \cos\theta}{4} \quad (5)$$

The enlargement of crystal size due to doping of nickel within magnesium ferrite is consistent with the earlier findings [20]. Crystallite sizes calculated by three methods are also consistent. According to Deraz et al., the peaks corresponding to (511), (440) and (220) are more responsive to the oxygen ion, cations on octahedral and tetrahedral parameters [21]. As nickel ions are very much prone to occupy B sites, thus the intensities of these respective planes increased with incorporation of nickel.

Figure 1: X-ray diffractograms of annealed (a) MgFe_2O_4 spinel and (b) $\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ spinel

Table 1: Crystal parameters calculated from X-ray diffraction data for MgFe_2O_4 and $\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$

Parameters	MgFe_2O_4	$\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$
Bragg's diffraction angle corresponding to (311)	35.604	35.610
FWHM (Radians)	0.023	0.021
Lattice constant (Å)	8.353	8.354
Unit cell Volume (Å) ³	582.842	582.960
Crystallite size [Scherrer formula] (nm)	6.325	6.896

Crystallite size [Williamson-Hall's method] (nm)	9.110	9.934
Crystallite size [SSP method] (nm)	6.977	7.608
Lattice strain	0.018	0.016
Micro strain	0.005	0.005
Stacking fault	0.447	0.447
Dislocation density (lines/m ²)	0.025	0.021

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy analysis

FTIR was performed on pure and nickel-doped magnesium ferrite to identify the quality of the spinel and functional groups. Figure 2 shows the spectrum of pure and Ni-doped MgFe₂O₄ within a range from 400 cm⁻¹ to 4000 cm⁻¹. The frequencies peaking at 555.38 cm⁻¹ and 413.25 cm⁻¹ confirm the formation of spinel ferrite material for pure magnesium ferrite and for nickel-doped magnesium ferrite 421.65 cm⁻¹ and 578.23 cm⁻¹ show the peak for the presence of spinel ferrite material[28]It shows the cation distribution and chemical modifications at octahedral and tetrahedral sites in the spinel ferrite structure. The lower frequency (ν_2) vibration band was identified at 413.25 cm⁻¹ and 421.65 cm⁻¹ for pure and Ni-doped MgFe₂O₄, respectively. The higher frequency (ν_1) vibration band was identified at 555.38 cm⁻¹ and 578.23 cm⁻¹ for pure and Ni-doped MgFe₂O₄ respectively . The vibrationandcorrespond to the octahedral and tetrahedral stretching vibration of oxygen-iron ions at the B sites and A sites respectively[22]. These confirm the spinel ferrite structure. Using Waldron's method, the force constants were calculated for octahedral (K_o) sites and for tetrahedral (K_t) sites using the equations and as shown in Table 2. In figure 2(b) the peaks at 1348.28 cm⁻¹ and 3423.52 cm⁻¹ signifies the bending vibrations of O-H [23]. The bending mode of H₂O molecules is represented by the band at 1630.16 cm⁻¹.

$$K_t = 4\pi^2 c^2 \nu_1^2 \mu \quad (6)$$

$$K_o = 4\pi^2 c^2 \nu_2^2 \mu \quad (7)$$

Figure 2: FTIR spectra of annealed (a) MgFe_2O_4 spinel and (b) $\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ spinel

Table 2: Parameters calculated from FTIR data for MgFe_2O_4 and $\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$

Parameters	MgFe_2O_4	$\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$
ν_1	555.38	578.23
K_t	224.80	243.68
ν_2	413.25	421.65
K_o	124.47	129.58

Raman spectroscopy

Raman spectra of annealed MgFe_2O_4 and $\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ were captured and shown in Figure 3. With a good consistency with the published result [24], in this study five Raman active modes have been identified at 215.31 cm^{-1} , 333.29 cm^{-1} , 487.75 cm^{-1} , 555.04 cm^{-1} , and 715.42 cm^{-1} for MgFe_2O_4 . These modes are generally the indication of the movement of ions [25, 26]. Figure 3 (b) shows the Raman spectrum of nickel-doped magnesium ferrite. In the figure, the peak at 201.80 cm^{-1} corresponds to “symmetric bending” of “O-atom” with respect to the metal ion in the AO_4 unit within the synthesized nanoparticles [27]. The band corresponding to 310.19 cm^{-1} corresponds to “asymmetric bending” of oxygen. The band at 471.83 cm^{-1} corresponds to “asymmetric stretching” of the (Fe/Ni)–O bond. The band 693.81 cm^{-1} corresponds to the “symmetric breathing mode” of the AO_4 unit with a spinel lattice. Nickel ions may have a larger scattering cross-section for Raman scattering compared to the original magnesium or iron ions. This means that when a Raman photon interacts with a nickel ion, it is more likely to scatter, which can result in a decreased intensity of the desired Raman signal for nickel-doped magnesium ferrite. All Raman active modes shift

towards lower wavenumber in nickel-doped magnesium ferrite. This shift is related to the compressive strain present in the doped samples.[29]

Figure 3: Raman spectra of annealed (a) MgFe_2O_4 spinel and (b) $\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ spinel

UV-Vis analysis

The UV-Visible absorption spectra of magnesium ferrite and nickel-doped magnesium ferrite are shown in Figure 4(a). The optical energy band gaps of synthesized nanoparticles are shown in Figure 4(b). Using the Taucmodel (Equation 8), the optical band gap is determined.

$$(\alpha h\nu)^2 = B(h\nu - E_g)^n \quad (8)$$

Where B is a constant dependent on the transition probability, E_g is the optical band gap, h is Planck's constant, and n is an index, which is theoretically taken to be 2 for a direct allowed transition and a value of 1/2 for an indirect allowed transition. α is the absorption coefficient. In Figure 4(b), the linear region of the plot is extrapolated to find the intercept on the x-axis to find the direct energy gap. The value of the direct energy gap for pure magnesium ferrite is 2.83 eV, and for nickel-doped magnesium ferrite is 2.92 eV. The energy band gap of ferrite nanoparticles is closely associated with the electrical properties. More specifically, the energy band gap is the energy needed to move an electron from the valence band to the conduction band. Thus, it is important for practical applications.

Figure 4: (a) UV-Vis spectra, and (b) variation of $\alpha h\nu^2$ with photon energy of annealed MgFe_2O_4 spinel and $\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ spinel

Conclusions

Ni-doped $\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ and pure magnesium ferrite (MgFe_2O_4) were effectively synthesized using the solution-gelation auto combustion process. The produced ferrites' crystalline structure was characterized using the XRD technique, which showed a preferential orientation along the (311) plane with a cubical structure. The size of the crystallite was discovered to be between 6 and 10 nm after being calculated using a number of techniques, such as Scherrer's formula, Williamson-Hall's plot, and the size-strain plot. Spinel ferrite was identified as the material by FTIR and Raman investigation. According to the structural study, nickel-doped magnesium ferrite has numerous applications, including memory devices and medication delivery.

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